

Thermodynamics and Spatial Symmetry Breaking Forces

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In this note, we try to examine thermodynamics in terms of spatial symmetry breaking forces. Spatial symmetry breaking forces are the norm in Newtonian mechanics because one often has a force in a particular direction (not all directions) accelerating a particle. This leads to a kind of resonance energy associated with this spatial symmetry breaking because all particles within the object accelerate and move in the symmetry breaking direction as a collective motion. Thus, the overall object may be described by a single center-of-mass variable.

On the other hand, a Maxwell-Boltzmann (MB) gas at rest has forces (impulse hits) in all directions such that overall momentum is zero. This is an example of a force with symmetry. Another example is the electric field of a charge at rest.

We suggest that there are symmetry breaking forces in nature which may act on both collective symmetry breaking resonances and on symmetric forces and this is linked to thermodynamics which gives special preference to the notion of force in work which acts on a collective resonance type variable. We consider the cases of friction and the emission of radiation from an accelerating charge as examples.

Newtonian Mechanics and Spatial Symmetry Breaking Forces

In many, though not all, cases, Newtonian mechanics deals with spatial symmetry breaking forces which create a resonance energy in the direction of the broken symmetry. In particular, an object at rest has many particles which are characterized by a density and temperature. There are energy fluctuations, or collisions in the case of an MB gas, but it is possible to exert a symmetry breaking force in one direction and accelerate the object in this direction, hence creating a resonance in which all of the particles accelerate and move collectively (even though there is still the aspect of temperature which is a separate consideration). No energy is given to the symmetrical force system, i.e. the temperature does not increase.

Once the object is moving, one may exert another symmetry breaking force, either in the direction of motion or opposite to it (or in some other direction). The point we make is that this spatial symmetry breaking force usually acts only on the symmetry breaking resonance. It accelerates (in the positive or negative direction) the entire system. As noted, no energy is given to temperature which represents spatially symmetric forces. In particular, if one has an MB gas, there are impulse hits in all directions such that average momentum is zero and energy is spread out in all directions creating a pressure system which is like a force field.

In the case of a force of friction (for example between the floor and the object or the air and the object), a force is exerted which affects both the symmetry breaking resonance motion and the symmetric force system (temperature) of the object. In other words, there are energy effects on both. In particular, the symmetry breaking resonance loses energy and the symmetrical force system (temperature) gains energy. The fact that a single force, friction, creates energy shifts in two different kinds of resonances (one representing broken spatial symmetry and the other symmetric forces) leads to the notion of thermodynamics, because this situation differs from the usual $F = dp/dt$ where p is the center-of-mass motion. If one has a gas, there is still conservation

of momentum when friction transfers some hits to the gas, but if the container walls are heavy, the associated energy transfer to the gas is in the form of energy associated with a spatially symmetric force, i.e. an increased pressure.

The Case of an Accelerating Charge

Consider next the case of a charge at rest. It has a symmetric electrostatic potential and an electric field E . This symmetrical electrical field system represents symmetrical force because $F=qE$ for a test charge q . In other words, the electric field is somewhat analogous to the pressure field of an MB gas and energy within the gas is like $q\phi$, the potential energy of a test charge q at some position r from the center of the source charge. Following Newtonian conservative force considerations, $F = -\text{grad } \phi$ for the electrostatic case.

Next, consider the case of accelerating a combined source Q plus test charge q system. The test charge q has energy $q\phi$ which is like rest mass energy which should be accelerated by a force:

$$F = ma = q\phi a, \text{ where } a \text{ is acceleration } ((1))$$

The source for this force is, however, is the electric field (there is no other force to perform this acceleration), but if acceleration is constant, there is no usual drop-off of $1/r$ as in the force from Q , rather there is a constant force ((1)) in the direction of the symmetry breaking force. If ϕ drops a Q/r , then this force (piece of E in the direction of motion) has the form Q/r (not $1/r$ for $\text{grad } \phi$ with grad acting on $1/r$).

As a result, we argue that the accelerating charge has the still somewhat symmetrical force system associated with E (and B) fields attached to the charge, but also a new piece of E which drops in a different manner, $1/r$, and is associated with symmetry breaking motion. We argue that this is akin to the frictional object picture. Some energy from the work needed to accelerate the particle goes into the part of the fields (E, B) attached to the source charge Q , while some other energy is linked with spatial symmetry breaking E, B energy, namely that associated with the E piece $q\phi a$. This is a two energy system, with each energy associated with different types of forces (symmetrical and symmetry breaking) and so we suggest that one has a thermodynamical situation.

The Question of Retarded Time

In the electrostatic case, $F = -\text{grad } \phi = E q$, which is the usual Newtonian prescription for a conservative force. If this $\text{grad } \phi$ operation still holds in the moving frame (which it should because it measures changes in potential along a radius), with possibly the addition of other pieces (formally $F = qE + q \times B$) with $E = -\text{grad } \phi' - d/dt' A$ partial and $B = \text{grad } \times A$), then the symmetry breaking E piece (force) should follow from $\text{grad } \phi$ (as well as from the other pieces) it seems

. If this is the case, grad cannot act on $1/r$ in the denominator of $\phi = g Q/r$ where $g = 1/\sqrt{1-vv/cc}$ and r is written in terms of x', t' . There must, therefore, be a term in the numerator upon which grad may act. Such a term should be linked with the motion of the charge Q in the

spatial symmetry breaking direction it seems. In other words, it seems to be a time type of variable because motion involves a change in position in time.

How can one apply a physical reason for such a term? If one argues that a measurement of the E field at r,t (r measured from a fixed origin) is due to a signal traveling at the speed of light in a vacuum c, then this signal must have been sent before time t in order to arrive at r at time t. In particular, one has (1):

$$\text{Retarded time} = t - R/c \text{ where } R = |\mathbf{r} - \mathbf{r}'| \quad ((2))$$

Here \mathbf{r} is the position of the E or phi measurement at time t, and \mathbf{r}' is the position of the charge Q. Such a prescription allows for $-\text{grad } \phi$ to act on $t-r/c$ which is the approximation of ((2)) for large \mathbf{r} vectors with respect to \mathbf{r}' vectors.

((2)) is a major change in the way electromagnetism is viewed because it introduces a signal which travels at the speed of light c in a vacuum. In principle, one might think that light has nothing to do with an electromagnetic system or its forces. One needs, however, a constant force in ((2)) in order that $F_{\text{piece}} = -\text{grad } \phi q = q \phi \text{ acceleration}$. In particular, as shown in (1) p458, the use of retarded time leads to phi pieces in addition to Q/r , namely, $d(t-r/c)/dt \cdot r / (rr)$. Grad acting on this term becomes $d/d(t-r/c) f(t) \cdot d(t-r/c)/dr$. Here \mathbf{p} is the dipole moment $= Q\mathbf{r}'$ and $d\mathbf{p}/dt = q\mathbf{v}$. Thus grad acting on $d\mathbf{p}(t-r/c)/dt$ yields a term proportional to a which is required by ((1)).

The notion of retarded time was introduced in 1898 by Lenard and 1900 by Weichert (2), but is really a consequence of special relativity. In (1) it is shown explicitly that the electric field for a point charge in motion may be calculated using a retarded time (pp 474-475) and strictly from special relativity (p 498) and that the two results are identical. Special relativity automatically introduces the constant c (speed of light in a vacuum) and so applying it to a moving charge and its fields introduces the notion of an object with speed c into the E,B field system.

Electromagnetic Momentum Density

Formally, one may obtain an electromagnetic momentum density $C_1 \mathbf{E} \times \mathbf{B}$, where C_1 is a constant and E,B electric and magnetic fields. This momentum density appears in a continuity equation obtained from Maxwell's em equations, namely:

$$d/dt \text{ partial } (.5\epsilon_0 \mathbf{E} \cdot \mathbf{E} + .5/\mu_0 \mathbf{B} \cdot \mathbf{B}) + C_1 \text{ grad } \cdot (\mathbf{E} \times \mathbf{B}) = \mathbf{E} \cdot \mathbf{j} \quad ((3))$$

Here \mathbf{j} =current density which only exists in the spatial region in which charge is flowing. If one integrates ((3)) over a very large volume, one sees that $\mathbf{E} \times \mathbf{B}$ perpendicular to the surface multiplied by the surface area of a sphere $4\pi r^2$ is the momentum flow out of the sphere. For the E piece which tends as $1/r$, this value is nonzero, suggesting a loss of energy. This is the standard argument for radiation from an accelerating charge (1), but we suggest that this result is already implied by the work being done on an accelerating charge being converted into energy associated with spatial symmetry, i.e. $1/r^2 \mathbf{E}$ field pieces versus energy associated with spatial symmetry breaking i.e. $q \phi q$, just as in the friction case.

Conclusion

In conclusion, we suggest that in usual Newtonian situations, one deals with spatial symmetry breaking forces which lead to energy associated with symmetry breaking, i.e. a kind of resonance described by center-of-mass motion. In the Newtonian world, one, however, also has temperature which is associated with symmetric forces (such that overall momentum is 0). In certain cases, such as friction, work may remove energy from the symmetry breaking resonance and add some to the symmetrical force system. This is seen as a thermodynamical situation, but is really a somewhat more complicated force situation. We suggest that for a charge at rest, one has symmetric force, but argue that one must have a spatial symmetry breaking force appear if one accelerates the charge. These two kinds of forces are associated with different energies and again one has a thermodynamical scenario because two types of forces, symmetrical and spatial symmetry breaking, obtain energy instead of just one.

References

1. Reitz, J. and Milford, R. and Christy, R. Foundations of Electromagnetic Theory (Addison-Wesely, 1980)
2. https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Li%C3%A9nard%E2%80%93Wiechert_potential